

Understanding brain diversity across ontogeny and phylogeny within a single common space

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Introduction

An under-appreciated feature of the brain is its diversity, across species [1] and through development [4]. To gain a better understanding of how the brain differs and how this relates to behaviour, we must be able to synthesise and integrate diverse datasets. We previously demonstrated that one can describe grey matter (GM) in terms of its unique pattern of extrinsic connections to white matter (WM) tracts [7,9]. Major tracts can be reliably identified in diverse brains, e.g. humans and macaques [8,10], but the GM projections will differ. The patterns of GM connectivity can be compared across brains and used to probe brain phylogeny.

Here, we build upon this idea and tackle the challenge of unification across brain phylogeny and ontogeny. We present an integrative framework that uses connectivity patterns to map differences and similarities *across species and across ages*. First, we define a new library of tractography protocols for mapping WM tracts in neonates, in correspondence with those for the adult human and macaque brains [10]. We use these tracts to build a common connectivity space for mapping brain phylogeny and ontogeny and test the hypothesis of whether regions whose connections are developed later in humans coincide with regions higher in the evolutionary hierarchy.

Methods

We developed protocols for 42 WM tracts, in correspondence with the ones developed for the adult and macaque brain, in XTRACT [10]. The protocols used standard-space seed, waypoint, exclusion and termination masks (Fig 1a) and were defined analogously across diverse brains, although different in geometry and exact location. We used high-quality dMRI data from 33 neonates born and scanned at 40 weeks PMA using a bespoke setup, publicly released from the developing Human Connectome Project (dHCP), 20 subjects from the Human Connectome Project (HCP) and 6 high-quality post-mortem macaque datasets. Fibre orientations were modelled (up to 3 per voxel) [5] and used for probabilistic tractography [2,10] for each subject. Fig 1b examples group-averaged tractography results, demonstrating the correspondence across the adult human and macaque brain.

We constructed group-averaged connectivity blueprints [7] (i.e. patterns of connections of different cortical areas to WM) using WM tracts as landmarks for the neonate, adult human and macaque (Fig 1c-d). We compare GM connectivity profiles (rows of the blueprints) using Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [6] and find the row-wise minimum KL divergence, revealing the vertex-wise divergence in connectivity profiles across a group-pair (Fig 1e).

Results

Connectivity blueprints were constructed for each group (Fig 2a). We explored how connectivity divergence patterns compare across ontogeny and phylogeny. Fig 2b(iv) shows a joint divergence map with respect to the adult human (i.e. product of macaque-adult and neonate-adult in Fig 2b(ii-iii)). High values indicate regions that develop later in humans and are also higher in the evolutionary hierarchy. Fig 2b(v) shows an exclusive disjunction map of the two patterns, highlighting where one of the ontogeny and phylogeny divergences are high with respect to the other, but not both. The similarity pattern shown in Fig 2b(iv) is impressively similar to previous results [3]. Frontal, parietal and temporal regions that have evolved in humans from primates tend to mature more slowly. For example, frontal area 45 (involved in speech semantic processing), where big differences are expected between primate species, but also to be undeveloped during early life, is jointly divergent across ontogeny and phylogeny.

Conclusion

We presented a common space framework for probing differences across diverse brains using WM connections allowing new unique possibilities for exploring fundamental neuroscience questions. This framework may be used to compare connectivity across diverse brains and in doing so, make predictions of cortical features, such as cortical myelination or maps of functional activation [7].

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Figure 1. a) Tractography protocols are defined as sets of ROIs and rules, following XTRACT principles. b) Resultant tractography results and their correspondence across diverse brains. c) Data used for cross-species and lifespan comparisons. d) Connectivity blueprints (cortical vertices by tracts) built as the dot product of a whole-brain connectivity matrix (whole-brain WM voxels by cortical vertices) and vectorised XTRACT tracts (WM voxels by tracts). Rows are cortical connectivity patterns of a given cortical vertex; columns are cortical territories of tracts. e) Blueprints are compared using KLD, a measure of statistical similarity (step 1.), and divergence maps generated by finding the minimum row-wise KLD (step 2.) across vertices.

Figure 2. a) Cortical territories of example WM tracts (columns of the connectivity blueprint) for the neonate, adult and macaque. b) Divergence maps for macaque-neonate, neonate-adult and macaque-adult brains and joint/disjoint divergence of monkey and neonatal brain with respect to the adult brain. i-iii. Divergence (minimum KL divergence) was calculated for each vertex, comparing between the above groups, i.e. across the ontogeny (ii.) and phylogeny (iii.) dimension. Group blueprints were used. Small divergence values correspond to regions with more predictable connectivity patterns between the two considered groups. iv. Phylogeny-ontogeny joint-divergence map, calculated as the product of panels ii and iii with larger (red) values indicating that divergence to adult is greater both across phylogeny and ontogeny. This indicates regions that develop later in life, and also have evolved in primates. v. Phylogeny-ontogeny exclusive disjoint (exclusive OR) divergence map, calculated as the $(ii+iii)-2(ii*iii)$ (union minus the intersection). Larger (red) values indicate regions that either develop later in humans or have evolved in primates, but not both.